

The nasal mucosa of atlantic salmon – where chemoreception meets immunity

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Teleost fish represent the most ancient vertebrate with a dedicated mucosal immune system as defined by the mucosa-associated lymphoid tissues (MALTs) in their secondary lymphoid organs. Three MALTs are well-known in fish: gut-, skin-, and gill-associated lymphoid tissue. The recent discovery of another MALT in fish, the nasopharynx-associated lymphoid tissue (NALT) in the olfactory organ, provided another perspective into the evolution of mucosal immunity by moving the emergence of vertebrate NALT to at least 100 million years earlier. The nasal microenvironment underlines the crossroads between olfaction, one of the most ancient sensory systems, and immunity, which is the system and mechanism that has protected fish for several hundred million years. Our understanding of such an interaction is limited. Using Atlantic salmon as a model, we explored the structural and molecular features of a teleost fish nasal mucosa and investigated how different environmental stressors modulate their mucosal barrier functions. The nasal epithelium contains lymphocytes and goblet cells, where the latter are pronouncedly situated on the mucosal tip. Isolated nasal leukocytes are responsive to bacterial and viral-associated molecular patterns as well as to oxidative chemical stressors. The olfactory organ expresses the immunoglobulins IgM and IgT and their transcription is modulated by bacterial and parasitic infections. Environmental stressors such as thermal stress, toxicants, and infection could drive changes to the transcriptomic landscape of the olfactory organ, notably modifying the pathways involved in cytokine activity and redox homeostasis. In addition, structural features exhibit plasticity towards changes in the environment, particularly to oxidative stressors. In a series of studies, we have provided insights into the nasal immunity of Atlantic salmon, laying groundworks for its future exploration as target for immunoprophylaxis.

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